
Development of a software module for recognizing vertebral compression fractures using artificial intelligence technologies

By

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Abstract

The topic of the diploma project: "*Development of a software module for recognizing vertebral compression fractures using machine learning*" was written by Aisara Sergalieva, Shaidarov Daryn, Boranshina Dilnaz, students of Big Data Analysis, Astana IT University.

The diploma project consists of 51 pages, 4 chapters, 9 tables, 22 figures, and 35 references.

The aim of this work is to develop and evaluate a software module capable of automatically detecting vertebral compression fractures from spinal X-ray images using artificial intelligence and computer vision techniques. The subject of the work is the development and testing of a hybrid machine learning system based on models such as YOLOv8, ResNet-18, and U-Net.

The objectives were to study modern AI approaches in medical diagnostics, define system requirements and evaluation metrics, collect and preprocess annotated spinal X-ray data, develop and train YOLOv8, ResNet, and U-Net models, implement and test the architecture, and evaluate model performance using standard metrics.

Among the models, YOLOv8 demonstrated the highest performance with a mean average precision of 78.60%, outperforming U-Net (75.80%) and ResNet-18 (classification accuracy of 71.30%). YOLOv8 also showed superior results in localizing multiple fracture zones with high speed and precision, making it suitable for real-time clinical use.

The results of the study confirm the effectiveness of using a hybrid deep learning approach to detect vertebral compression fractures. A user-friendly web application was developed to enable real-time spinal X-ray analysis, providing an accessible diagnostic tool for medical professionals.

The findings of this study highlight the potential of intelligent diagnostic systems to improve the speed and accuracy of clinical decision-making, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes.

Key words: Vertebral compression fracture, spinal X-ray, YOLOv8, ResNet-18, U-Net, computer vision, medical image analysis, real-time detection.

Authors' declaration

We declare that the work in this thesis was carried out in accordance with the requirements of the University's Regulations and that it has not been submitted for any other academic award. Except where indicated by specific references in the text, the work is the candidates' own work. Work done in collaboration with, or with the assistance of, others, is indicated as such. Any views expressed in the thesis are those of the authors.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies and medicine, special attention is being paid to the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision (CV) in disease diagnostics. These technologies not only improve the accuracy of pathology detection but also accelerate the interpretation of medical images, thereby reducing the workload on specialists. One of the most common and underestimated conditions, especially among elderly patients, is vertebral compression fractures (VCF).

According to recent studies, more than 1.4 million cases of vertebral compression fractures are recorded worldwide every year [1]. These fractures are particularly prevalent among individuals over the age of 50, especially postmenopausal women, and lead to reduced mobility, chronic pain, and a high risk of recurrent injuries. Moreover, various estimates suggest that 66% to 75% of such cases go undiagnosed due to the subtle visual signs on X-ray images and the high workload of radiologists [2].

Traditional diagnostic methods, including X-ray imaging, have limited sensitivity, ranging from 49% to 58%, which leads to a high number of missed pathologies. In contrast, methods such as computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provide more accurate results but require more time, resources, and highly qualified personnel. Furthermore, existing clinical protocols often lack unified guidelines for diagnosing and classifying VCFs, especially in mild cases [1].

Considering these challenges, the application of intelligent systems for the automatic analysis of spinal medical images becomes especially relevant. Machine learning methods, particularly neural network architectures, can significantly improve diagnostic accuracy

and automate key steps such as fracture detection, classification, and compression level assessment. Thus, the development of intelligent diagnostic tools represents a meaningful contribution to the advancement of digital medicine.

The developed software module for automatic recognition of vertebral compression fractures has high practical value. This tool can be integrated into clinical workflows as a radiology assistant, reducing the likelihood of diagnostic errors, accelerating image analysis, and providing support in regions with a shortage of medical specialists. The solution will be implemented in Python using the PyTorch and Streamlit frameworks and is capable of operating in real-time. Additionally, the module can be used for educational purposes in training specialists in the field of medical imaging and diagnostics.

This study aims to develop a software module based on machine learning models that can automatically detect, classify, and assess the severity of vertebral compression fractures in spinal X-ray images.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives have been set:

1. To study modern approaches to the use of artificial intelligence in medical diagnostics and review existing solutions.
2. To define the requirements for the software module, data structure, and performance evaluation metrics.
3. To collect and preprocess a dataset of annotated spinal X-ray images, including the presence, type, and severity of fractures.
4. To develop and train the following models: YOLOv8 for localization, ResNet and U-Net for classification.
5. To implement the model architecture and conduct its testing.
6. To evaluate the models' performance using standard metrics and carry out a comparative analysis and formulate conclusions

Object of the study: the diagnostic process for vertebral compression fractures based on X-ray images. Subject of the study: the application of deep learning models (YOLOv8, ResNet, and U-Net) for the automatic detection and classification of vertebral compression fractures.

Chapter 1 presents an analysis of the subject area, including issues of radiographic diagnostics, modern methods of automatic fracture recognition, and the formulation of technical requirements for the software module.

Chapter 2 focuses on the development and training of the YOLOv8, ResNet, and U-Net architectures, as well as the stages of data preparation based on real medical images.

Chapter 3 covers the technical implementation of the software module, testing results, model comparison, and interpretation of the obtained outputs. The conclusion summarizes the work, evaluates the achievement of the research objectives, and outlines directions for future development.

1.1 Diagnostic Challenges Based on Radiographic Data

Despite the widespread availability and use of radiography as the primary method for diagnosing vertebral compression fractures (VCFs), its effectiveness in clinical practice remains limited. This is due to the method's low sensitivity, inadequate visualization of soft tissues, and lack of standardized protocols for interpreting obtained images. According to [1] (2024), the sensitivity of radiography in detecting vertebral compression fractures is only 49.2% for the thoracic spine and 57.8% for the lumbar spine. This means that a significant proportion of fractures remain undetected during initial evaluation, especially if the injury is mild or chronic in nature. At the same time, the method has high specificity, making it acceptable for confirming but not for excluding the diagnosis.

One of the key problems is the inability to reliably distinguish between acute and chronic fractures on radiographic images. The degree of vertebral body compression can be minimal, and the visual signs of injury are often ambiguous. As noted by [2], a considerable number of such fractures are mistakenly interpreted as age-related degenerative changes or completely overlooked in reports. This leads to delayed treatment, intensified pain, and the development of spinal deformities.

An additional complexity is the human factor: due to high workloads, radiologists may overlook subtle signs. [1] emphasize that even when radiographic signs of VCF are present, the fracture is omitted from the final report in 20–30% of cases. This is

particularly relevant in emergency departments and outpatient settings.

Furthermore, clinical practice lacks a universal approach to describing and classifying VCFs. Existing systems, such as the Genant grading method, require specific training and are not always feasible within a typical clinical workflow. This further reduces the consistency and reproducibility of diagnoses based solely on radiographic data.

To clearly illustrate the comparative characteristics of key imaging modalities used in diagnosing vertebral compression fractures, the following table is presented.

Table 1.1: *Comparison of Imaging Modalities for VCF Diagnosis*

Modality	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Soft Tissue Visualization	Cost	Availability	Exam. Time (min)
Radiography	49–58	~95	No	Low	Very high	5–10
CT	95–98	~97	Partial	Medium	Moderate	10–20
MRI	90–95	~90	Yes	High	Limited	30–45

Based on data from [1] and clinical practice guidelines

In the study by [3], a case was reported involving a 67-year-old patient presenting with acute lower back pain following minor trauma. The initial radiographic examination showed no pathological changes; however, a subsequent CT scan confirmed a compression fracture of the T12 vertebral body. This case highlights the limited capability of radiography in the primary visualization of vertebral compression fractures and underscores the need for more sensitive imaging techniques in ambiguous clinical situations.

Thus, in light of the limited sensitivity of radiography, variability in interpretation, and absence of standardized protocols, there is a clear need for supplementary diagnostic tools. In particular, models based on computer vision and artificial intelligence are being considered as potentially effective methods for automating and improving the accuracy of vertebral compression fracture diagnosis.

1.2 Analysis of existing systems

Over the past decade, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into medical diagnostics has accelerated significantly. Numerous companies and start-ups have introduced automated systems designed to support radiologists by detecting and classifying abnor-

malities in radiological images. This section provides a brief overview of several leading AI-based platforms currently used in clinical practice, particularly those relevant to bone and spinal fracture detection. Zebra Medical Vision is an advanced AI platform that analyzes medical images such as X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs to detect early signs of various pathologies, including cardiovascular disease, lung and breast cancers, and bone fractures. The system is capable of identifying conditions before they become visible to the human eye. Its algorithms are designed for early diagnosis of osteoporosis, coronary artery calcification, and emphysema, contributing to improved patient outcomes through timely intervention. Viz.ai is a clinically deployed AI platform launched in 2016 that includes specialized modules such as Viz Neuro Suite, Viz Radiology Suite, and Viz Cardio Suite. The system uses deep learning models to analyze medical images in real time and immediately notify the appropriate medical professionals. In radiology, it helps accelerate the detection of stroke, vascular abnormalities, and other acute conditions, reducing time to diagnosis and treatment. The platform is currently used across numerous hospital systems in the United States and Europe. Avicenna AI, a French medical AI company, introduced the CINA platform in 2018 to reduce radiologists' workload by providing automated detection of critical conditions using CT data. One of its modules, CINA-VCF, is specifically designed to detect vertebral compression fractures and assess their severity using CT scans. The system offers localization and classification, supporting decision-making in emergency and outpatient settings. BoneView by Gleamer is an FDA-cleared AI tool used to analyze bone X-rays. It assists radiologists in detecting fractures, dislocations, bone lesions, and effusions. The system is integrated into more than 2,500 healthcare institutions across 45 countries and processes over 40 million radiographic studies annually. Although the aforementioned systems have demonstrated high clinical relevance and technical performance, the majority of them focus on CT or whole-body bone imaging. Only a limited number offer automated detection of vertebral compression fractures specifically from spinal X-ray images, which are more widely available and cost-effective in many healthcare settings. Moreover, several systems are designed as proprietary platforms that do not offer customization for research and experimentation. Therefore, this project addresses an important gap by developing a YOLOv8-based open model tailored for detecting vertebral compression fractures from spinal X-ray images. By focusing on the detection of subtle abnormalities in low-contrast radiographic data, the proposed system aims to provide an accessible, accurate, and adaptable solution for clinical and academic use.

1.3 Application of Machine Learning and Computer Vision for Image Analysis

Machine learning (ML) and computer vision (CV) methods are increasingly being adopted in the analysis of medical imaging, including radiography, CT, and MRI. In the context of diagnosing vertebral compression fractures (VCFs), three main tasks are of particular importance: detection, classification.

Fracture detection is typically performed using object detection models such as YOLOv8, which demonstrate high precision in localizing pathological areas. For example, [4] utilized the YOLOv5 architecture in conjunction with VGG to automatically detect and classify VCFs on spinal X-ray images, achieving 92.4% accuracy on the test dataset.

To determine the type and severity of a fracture, architectures like ResNet are employed due to their high sensitivity to visual patterns of compression. In particular, [4] used ResNet to classify types of compression fractures (wedge, biconcave, crush) on spinal X-ray images, achieving over 93% accuracy on the test set.

Segmentation, the final step, is addressed using models such as U-Net, which enable pixel-level delineation of deformed vertebral regions. [5] applied a modified U-Net architecture to evaluate lesion area and degree of compression, reporting improved segmentation accuracy compared to manual annotation.

The use of neural network approaches offers several key advantages:

- Increased diagnostic accuracy and sensitivity;
- Reduced inter-observer variability;
- Automation of routine tasks in high-volume clinical workflows;
- Applicability in remote or underserved regions with limited access to specialists.

A comprehensive review by [6] confirms that deep learning models significantly outperform traditional approaches in diagnosing VCFs, particularly when using radiographic data of limited image quality.

Thus, modern deep neural network architectures provide robust, reproducible, and scalable outcomes in the analysis of vertebral compression fractures, making them a promising direction in clinical diagnostic practice.

1.4 Problem Statement

Given the high prevalence of vertebral compression fractures (VCFs) and the limited effectiveness of traditional diagnostic methods, there is a growing need for an intelligent software solution capable of automatically analyzing spinal X-ray images and detecting pathological signs. The problem addressed in this project involves developing a neural network-based software module that integrates detection, classification, and severity assessment using modern deep learning architectures.

1.4.1 Formulation of the Aim and Objectives of the Thesis

Aim—To develop a software module based on deep learning algorithms for the automatic detection, classification, and severity assessment of vertebral compression fractures on spinal X-ray images.

Objectives:

1. To study current machine learning and computer vision methods applied in medical diagnostics;
2. To define functional and architectural requirements for the software solution;
3. To collect and annotate a dataset of spinal X-ray images with labeled vertebral compression fractures;
4. To build a modular model architecture based on:
 - YOLOv8 – for detection and localization of potential fracture regions;
 - ResNet – for classification of fracture type;
 - U-Net combined with ResNet – for assessing the severity of compression;
5. To train and evaluate the model stack using the metrics Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC;

6. To develop a web-based interface in Streamlit and conduct usability testing of the prototype.

1.4.2 Requirements for the Software Module

1. Accept spinal X-ray images in digital formats (JPG/PNG);
2. Automatically detect and localize potential fracture areas (YOLOv8);
3. Classify fracture types (ResNet) and assess severity of compression (U-Net + ResNet);
4. Display predictions with visual labels and confidence scores on the images;
5. Support inference in both CPU and GPU modes;
6. Provide a user-friendly interface developed with Streamlit.

1.4.3 Data Requirements for Model Training

1. Spinal images in anteroposterior and lateral projections, preferably with high resolution;
2. Image formats: JPEG/PNG;
3. Availability of annotations in the form of bounding boxes (YOLO) and class labels (ResNet, U-Net);
4. Manual or semi-automated annotation performed by specialists;
5. Dataset must be split into training (80%) and test (20%) subsets;
6. Balanced class representation is essential (e.g., various fracture types and healthy samples).

1.4.4 Model Evaluation Criteria

1. **Accuracy** – proportion of correctly classified samples:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

2. **Precision** – proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

3. **Recall (Sensitivity)** – proportion of actual positives correctly identified:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

4. **F1-Score** – harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

5. **ROC-AUC (Receiver Operating Characteristic – Area Under the Curve)** – measures the model’s ability to distinguish between classes. It is defined as the area under the ROC curve:

$$AUC = \int_0^1 TPR(FPR^{-1}(x)) dx$$

where:

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \quad FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

1.5 Literature review

Table 1.2 gives a short summary of studies that examine the uses of machine learning and deep learning in medical image analysis. Collected information shows the authors, date, techniques, data sources, main outcomes and weaknesses for each paper.

Table 1.2: *Overview of AI Models Applied to Vertebral Imaging and Performance Metrics*

Authors	Data acquisition method and data type	Dataset size	Models used	Performance metrics
Zhang et al. (2024)	Digital radiographs of spinal compression fractures	1,747 images	Deep Residual Network	AUC: 0.99 (validation), 0.89–0.88 (external); Accuracy: 81.45%–96.62%
Shen et al. (2023)	X-ray images from hospital radiology departments	11,397 X-rays (training), 2,400 internal validation, 1,276 external validation	YOLO-XRAY (YOLOv5-based multitask detection network)	Internal: Accuracy = 97.41%, Sensitivity = 84.08%, Specificity = 97.25%; External: Accuracy = 96.85%
Xu et al. (2023)	X-ray images from 1,904 participants	2,609 images	ResNet-18 (transfer learning)	Accuracy: 95.9 (training), 77.7% (testing); Sensitivity: 88.7%
Zhang et al. (2023)	Retrospective CT images of thoracolumbar vertebral fractures	1,217 images (812 training, 120 validation, 285 test)	U-Net, Graph Convolutional Network, 3D-ResNet	Sensitivity = 95.23%, Specificity = 98.35%, Accuracy = 97.93%; AUC (A1–A4): 0.904–0.945
Paik et al. (2024)	Radiographs of patients from Ansan Hospital	487 with fractures, and 141 normal	Deep learning algorithms (Mask R-CNN, YOLO)	Mask R-CNN Accuracy = 85.7%; Cascade R-CNN = 80.8%; YOLOACT = 73.4%; YOLOv5-1 = 75.7%

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Authors	Data acquisition method and data type	Dataset size	Models used	Performance metrics
Arakawa et al. (2024)	Data from The Jikei University Hospital	709 X-ray images	Mask R-CNN	Accuracy = 85.7%
Han et al. (2024)	Lateral radiographs of L1 vertebra data of 852 patients	–	SVM, RF, XGBoost, KNN	KNN Accuracy = 76.6%
Ryu et al. (2023)	Lumbar spine lateral radiographs	2073 training, 200 test images	U-Net (ResNet encoder)	Accuracy = 96%, Dice score = 0.947
Chiari-Correia et al. (2023)	Lumbar spine MRIs from 91 patients	1865 training, 208 validation, 198 test	K-NN	ROC AUC = 0.97, Accuracy = 93.3%
Zhang et al. (2024)	Vertebrae X-ray images	1,076 images	ResNet-50	–
Nguyen Trung et al. (2021)	Spine X-ray images from 5,000 studies	10,468 images	ResNet-50, Sparse R-CNN	AUROC = 0.8861
Wang et al. (2024)	X-ray, CT, and MRI images	11,417 CT scans and 19,718 vertebrae	Faster R-CNN with ResNet18 backbone	AUC = 0.982, Sensitivity = 0.891, Specificity = 0.989
Chen et al. (2024)	100 patients' lumbar spine MRIs	–	Deep neural network models	SymTC model, Dice = 0.94

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Table 1.2 – continued from previous page

Authors	Data acquisition method and data type	Dataset size	Models used	Performance metrics
Ono et al. (2023)	Lumbar vertebra images	4,143 images	YOLOv5, CNN	Accuracy = 84%, Sensitivity = 76%, Specificity = 89%
Kim et al. (2021)	Lumbar spine X-ray	339 images	U-Net	Dice coefficient = 0.929
Yabu et al. (2021)	MRI images	1,624 images	VGG16, VGG19, DenseNet201, ResNet50	Sensitivity = 88.1%, Specificity = 87.9%, Accuracy = 88%
Karnuta et al. (2023)	X-rays of the knee (anteroposterior view)	4,724 X-rays	–	Accuracy = 97.4%
Chen et al. (2022)	MRI images from 1,099 patients	1,877 images	Ensemble model	Accuracy = 74%
Cheng et al. (2022)	X-ray images from 390 patients	–	YOLO, ResUNet, Random Forest	Precision = 74%
Kim et al. (2023)	Radiological images of the foot	–	InceptionResNet, MobileNetV1, ResNet152V2	F1-score: 0.837, Accuracy: 86.1%

Experts in Shandong Province did a study on the effectiveness of deep residual networks in recognising fresh vertebral compression fractures seen on digital spine radiography images. The work analysed data from five institutions. The evaluation determined that the model achieved a high AUC of 0.99. Besides, this model did better than other deep learning methods and kept being highly reliable when using older VCFs [7]. The system was built to automatically recognise and measure how severe osteoporotic vertebral fractures are in standard X-ray images. The model went through learning with

more than 11,000 chest X-rays from six community health centres in Shanghai. The performance of the deep learning system was similar to that of trained radiologists. For the internal test, the model reached 97.4% accuracy, had sensitivity of 84.1% and a specificity of 97.3%, whilst in the external test, accuracy was 96.9%, sensitivity was 83.4% and specificity was 94.7%. The tool seemed most effective at spotting fractures that were moderate and severe [8]. A deep learning model using the ResNet-18 architecture was proposed and tested to find and categorise vertebral compression fractures seen on X-rays. In all, 1,904 patients were included from the four participating hospitals. The model performed exceptionally well, scoring 0.850 in the test set, 0.829 in the prospective set and within 0.757-0.832 in external sets, exceeding many radiologists in noticing acute, chronic and pathological VCFs [9]. With computational power, the team of researchers used images of 1,217 patients' spines on CT scans and a convolutional neural network to develop such a system. This study introduces a method to integrate several networks at different times. Localization and classification problems were solved with U-net and U-GCN models. The fracture detection accuracy was 97.93% and the models had 95.23% of all cases detected correctly [10]. Deep learning is expected to be very helpful in locating VCFs on simple radiographs and aids doctors. For this research paper, the authors work with three deep learning models called Cascade Mask R-CNN, YOLOACT and YOLOv5. This research mainly trains models on over 400 radiographs with 598 known fractures using MRI, so they can spot signs of fractures in radiographs. The research found that Musk R-CNN reached higher levels of accuracy (85.7%), high sensitivity (79.8%) and specificity (89.4%) [11]. Experts at Jikei University and with Shimadzu Corporation have created software aided by artificial intelligence. The system is designed to diagnose vertebral fractures by using two deep learning models. As explained in the article, the software can spot 6 important points on vertebrae and measure their ratios of height [12].

It was revealed by recent scientific studies that adding radiomic features and machine learning to X-ray analysis can improve the ability to detect cancer at an early stage. In the paper, the authors used the Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, eXtreme Gradient Boosting, K-Nearest Neighbours and LightGBM as five algorithms. As shown in this analysis, the K-nearest neighbours algorithm achieved an accuracy of 76.6% among the test cases [13]. Analysis found that the multi-task model is much better at handling multiprocessing tasks than the single-task model. In addition, the multi-task deep learning model adapted from U-Net matched results with a high accuracy of 96%. The study found that the multitasking model can identify osteoporotic fractures of the spine and determine

the levels of the vertebrae at the same time from lateral X-rays of the lumbar spine. An additional result was a high Dice score of 0.947 [14]. A type of artificial neural network trained with 3D radiomics used T1-weighted lumbar spine MRI scans from 91 patients to identify fracture type. A model was built using radiomic features from 3D-segmented vertebra. The results indicate the model is reliable, with a 0.98 ROC AUC, 95% accuracy on cross-test and 0.97 ROC AUC and 93.3% accuracy on independent test set. This way of examining images appears helpful for radiologists to place fractures correctly [15]. To classify osteoporotic vertebral fractures into three groups, a deep learning method was built using X-ray images. The framework used the ResNet-50 architecture along with transfer learning. Training the model on two different datasets was the main goal and then we compared them. For this purpose, the model trained on RadImageNet which used medical images and on ImageNet which featured natural images. Results indicate that the RadImageNet-based model is more accurate than the ImageNet-based model in detecting diseases [16]. A method that uses deep learning was built to help detect and classify spinal problems in X-ray images. They prepared a detailed database of 10,468 spine X-rays involving 13 spine abnormalities and taught convolutional neural networks to recognise them at both image and lesion levels. For telling normal and abnormal scans apart, the system scored an AUROC of 88.6% and found lesions with an average precision of 33.6%. This work gives a useful reference and accessible tools to advance spine diagnosis using radiographs [17]. A system using deep learning was built to identify five vertebral diseases: osteoporotic vertebral compression fractures, osteoporotic fractures, Schmorl's nodes, Kummell's disease and posterior structure. According to the paper, the system was split into two modules—ResNet18-Faster R-CNN for detecting the vertebrae and ResNet50 for the classification task. Using ResNet18 in Faster R-CNN, I got an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.982. The sensitivity for detecting four types of vertebral diseases was 0.919 and the specificity was 0.995 for ResNet50. The system achieved excellent results and remained strong for the four vertebral disease diagnoses [18]. Scientists from the University of Miami reviewed different methods for deep neural networks to segment spinal regions in lumbar spine MRI. For 15 advanced DNN models, they tested both convolutional and Transformer NN, to let computers identify and label vertebrae and discs they detect in MRI images. It was discovered that using both CNNs and Transformers together got the highest results, especially once the augmented data was added [19]. A computer model was created and examined by researchers to automatically recognise normal, old or current osteoporotic fractures in the lumbar spine on radiographs. Based on images of 4,143 vertebrae from two Japanese hospitals, the

team trained a group of neural networks (CNNs) and were able to correctly categorise fracture types 84% of the time. This article explains that using this approach may replace MRI and helps clinicians in situations where MRI is unavailable [20]. This research team presented a way to use deep learning for automatic detection of the vertebrae in lateral X-rays of the thoracic and lumbar spines and then measure the vertebral compression ratio. The researchers created their model using a multidilated recurrent residual U-Net architecture. The model achieved excellent results by reaching a Dice similarity coefficient of 0.929 on a dataset of 339 images. The findings show that automated deep learning is effective for assessing vertebral compression fractures in the clinic [21]. With convolutional neural network-based algorithms, there is accurate identification of osteoporotic vertebral fractures in MR images. The model achieved 88.1% sensitivity, 87.9% specificity and 88% accuracy. According to the findings, AI can participate in early detection of osteoporotic vertebral fractures which might benefit patient outcomes[22]. A programme was made to automatically find knee arthroplasty implant models through plain radiographs. Nearly 3,500 images were used to train the deep learning model and it was tested using 744 images from several centres. The model achieved 97.4% accuracy and an ROC area of 0.989 for classifying nine implant designs by four manufacturers [23]. Researchers from China used deep learning to differentiate fresh vertebral compression fractures on digital radiography by comparing them to MRI as the reference. Among the 1,877 VCFs, 1,099 were used, split between a development and a test dataset. The ensemble model scored an AUC of 0.80, was right 74% of the time, had a sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 68%. Though AP views performed moderately well, with an AUC of 0.77, the highest scores for accuracy and area under the curve were seen for lateral images used with grade 3 and crush-type fractures [24]. These scientists used YOLO, ResNet, UNet and random forest classifiers as part of a machine learning model to tell apart thoracolumbar compression fractures and burst fractures from X-ray images, then confirmed using CT or MRI scans. The model, tested on 390 patients, was able to diagnose compression fractures with high accuracy of 74% and burst fractures with accuracy of 94%, doing better than earlier X-ray-based methods. Even though AI assists in recognising fractures, it has not yet achieved the same accuracy for foot fractures as traditional tools [25]. So, a new AI system was built using a sequence of transfer learning convolutional neural networks, namely InceptionResNetV2, MobileNetV1 and ResNet152V2 together with image boosting practises like contrast-limited adaptive histogram and augmentation [26].

Chapter 2

Model development and training

2.1 Data collection

The figure below depicts the dataset comprising X-ray images employed for analysis.

Figure 2.1: *Dataset*

The dataset includes 10,466 spine X-ray images taken from the open dataset VinDr-SpineXR [27]. The images are presented in the DICOM format. This format was specially developed for storing digital medical images and documents. The images were collected from 4,000 different studies conducted by the authors Hieu Huy Pham, Hieu Nguyen Trung, and Ha Quy Nguyen. The data is divided into 2 types, namely the training set -

8,389 images, and the test set - 2,077 images. Furthermore, the data includes CSV files with radiologist annotations consisting of thirteen lesion types, namely: Ankylosis, Disc space narrowing, Enthesophytes, Foraminal stenosis, Fracture, Osteophytes, Sclerotic lesion, Spondylolsthesis, Subchondral sclerosis, Surgical implant, Vertebral collapse, Foreign body, and Other lesions.

2.2 Data Preparation

The illustrations below demonstrate the effect of data augmentation techniques on a medical image.

Figure 2.2: *Before preprocessing*

Figure 2.3: *After preprocessing*

A data augmentation pipeline was used to prepare the X-rays for training. Firstly, images were converted to grayscale to reduce color complexity. The grayscale is widely used as a preprocessing step as this technique simplifies data processing. The next steps were to align the images and crop the empty areas on the images. To enhance the visibility of vertebrae and fractures, histogram equalization was performed. Histogram alignment helps to better analyze bone structure on X-rays by improving contrast. This technique adjusts brightness levels to better highlight anatomical features. The images were then resized to 640×640 pixels to ensure compatibility with the YOLOv8 model architecture. This resolution preserves high image quality, which is crucial for accurate pathology

detection. Additionally, standardizing the image size across the dataset allows for more efficient use of computational resources.

To enhance the diversity and robustness of the training dataset, data augmentation techniques were employed. Specifically, random rotations within a range of ± 5 degrees and translations of up to ± 15 pixels in any direction were applied. These transformations helped the model become less sensitive to small changes in image orientation, which often happen in real-world data. By seeing such variations during training, the model learned to generalize better and handled minor distortions or shifts in the input more effectively. Additionally, all images were converted to 3-channel RGB format. This step ensured compatibility with convolutional neural networks. Even if the original images were grayscale, converting them to RGB format allowed the model to work correctly.

2.3 Description of Machine Learning Models for Automatic Compression Fracture Recognition

2.3.1 Model 1: YOLOv8 for automatic detection of vertebral compression fractures

Detecting vertebral compression fractures (VCFs) on spinal X-ray images is a typical object detection task, which requires not only classification but also precise localization of pathological changes. Among existing deep learning architectures for such tasks, YOLO (You Only Look Once) has proven to be an effective single-stage algorithm capable of real-time detection without compromising accuracy.

The latest version — YOLOv8 — features an improved architecture with C2f blocks in the backbone, an optimized SPPF module (Spatial Pyramid Pooling-Fast), and a compact detection head. According to [28], YOLOv8 outperforms previous versions (YOLOv5/6/7) in terms of detection accuracy and inference speed across a variety of datasets.

The effectiveness of YOLO-family architectures in medical imaging has been tested by numerous studies. For instance, [29] proposed YOLO-SG, a modified version of YOLO designed for detecting small objects in medical images, including low-contrast regions. The model achieved significant improvements in accuracy through the use of saliency maps — a feature particularly valuable for analyzing subtle fracture patterns on X-ray scans. In addition, a study by [30] demonstrated that YOLOv5 achieved high accuracy (76.9%)

in detecting and classifying pressure ulcers and outperformed conventional convolutional networks. This confirms the versatility and adaptability of YOLO when applied to medical imaging, where high sensitivity is essential for detecting complex visual abnormalities.

Thus, YOLOv8 was selected as the baseline detection model for automatic vertebral compression fracture detection due to its high accuracy, fast inference time, strong generalization on small-scale medical datasets, and compatibility with real-time clinical environments. The YOLOv8 architecture is composed of three primary components: the Backbone, the Neck, and the Head (Figure 2.2). This structure enables efficient feature extraction, multi-scale information fusion, and object prediction — all of which are especially critical for detecting subtle vertebral compression fractures (VCFs) on spinal X-ray images.

The Backbone is responsible for extracting semantic features from the input image. YOLOv8 introduces a new building block called C2f (Cross-Stage Partial Fusion), which improves computational efficiency while preserving spatial information and gradient flow. In implementation, this block is reflected as CSPLayer_2Conv on the architecture diagram. YOLOv8 also incorporates a Spatial Pyramid Pooling-Fast (SPPF) module to enhance the receptive field by aggregating spatial features at multiple scales, allowing the network to capture global context even in localized lesions.

The Neck aggregates features across different resolution levels using a structure similar to a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN). It performs upsampling, concatenation, and further convolutional processing to fuse both low-level and high-level features. On the diagram, these operations are shown as Upsample, Contact, and ConvModule layers. This hierarchical fusion is essential in medical imaging tasks where abnormalities may vary in size, shape, and location.

The Prediction Head generates outputs at three scales, enabling the detection of small, medium, and large objects. Notably, YOLOv8 uses an anchor-free detection head, eliminating the need for predefined anchor boxes. This simplifies training and improves adaptability across domains. As shown in Figure 2.2, each branch in the head outputs bounding box coordinates, class probabilities, and objectness scores — essential for downstream classification and severity assessment. Compared to previous YOLO versions, YOLOv8 demonstrates measurable improvements in both mean Average Precision and inference time. According to [31], these optimizations make YOLOv8 especially suitable for real-time fracture detection tasks in clinical practice.

Figure 2.4 Illustrates the detailed architecture of the YOLOv8 model, which is composed of three main components: the Backbone for feature extraction, the Neck for feature fusion at different scales, and the Head for final object detection and classification.

Figure 2.4: Detailed structure of YOLOv8 [32]

The training process of the YOLOv8 model in this project consisted of several scientifically grounded steps, including annotation transformation, dataset configuration, and parameter-tuned model training. Each stage was aimed at maximizing model generalizability and robustness for spinal X-ray analysis.

1. Annotation Conversion: CSV to YOLO Format.

The initial bounding box annotations were provided in CSV format, listing coordinates and object class labels. These annotations were converted to YOLO-compatible '.txt' files in the format '(x_center, y_center, width, height)' with values normalized relative to image size. Class labels were mapped to numerical indices corresponding to YOLO's internal structure. Each annotation file was named identically to its associated image,

ensuring correct alignment during training.

Normalizing coordinates allows for model invariance to image resolution — a critical aspect when working with datasets collected from heterogeneous medical sources. Although the dataset in this study consisted of X-ray images from a single source, normalization ensured model invariance to resolution, which is critical for deployment in real-world clinical environments.

2. Dataset Configuration: data.yaml.

A custom ‘data.yaml’ file was created to define dataset structure and model behavior. It contained:

1. Paths to ‘train’ and ‘val’ directories with annotated images;
2. The number of classes (‘nc: 13’);
3. A list of class names, including ‘fracture’, ‘osteophytes’, ‘tumor’, and other pathological features.

This configuration ensures interoperability between the Ultralytics YOLO training engine and the medical dataset. It allows for scalability and modularization when integrating additional diagnostic categories in future expansions.

3. Model Training.

Model training was conducted using the Ultralytics YOLO library with pretrained weights (‘yolov8n.pt’) initialized on the COCO dataset. This enabled efficient transfer learning, significantly reducing the number of training epochs needed for convergence.

The following hyperparameters were applied:

1. Epochs: 100 — allowing the model sufficient time to generalize;
2. Image size: 640×640 — standard for balancing speed and detail;
3. Batch size: 16 — selected to balance training speed and GPU memory constraints;
4. Initial learning rate (‘lr0’): 0.001 — chosen based on Ultralytics recommendations;

A series of augmentations such as rotation, brightness shifts, and contrast scaling was also applied to improve robustness against noise and anatomical variation.

This procedure produced a fine-tuned YOLOv8 model with effective spatial awareness and generalization capability across real-world X-ray data, optimized for automatic detection of vertebral compression fractures.

2.3.2 Selection of Optimizer

In this project, the YOLOv8 model was trained using the AdamW optimizer — a modified version of the classical Adam algorithm that introduces decoupled weight decay for improved regularization.

Unlike standard Adam, which applies L2 regularization by modifying the gradients, AdamW separates the weight decay term from the gradient updates. This decoupling leads to more stable convergence, reduced overfitting, and better generalization performance, especially in high-dimensional data domains such as medical image analysis.

This choice was particularly well-suited to the dataset used in this project, which consisted of spinal X-ray images with limited volume and class imbalance. In such scenarios, adaptive learning rates and controlled weight penalization are essential to maintain sensitivity to subtle features (e.g., micro-fractures) while avoiding overfitting to background patterns or noise.

Furthermore, AdamW’s robustness in handling sparse gradients and complex decision boundaries makes it a compelling option for deep object detection models like YOLOv8. Its adoption has been recommended in recent literature and in the Ultralytics framework itself for fine-tuning models on domain-specific datasets.

2.3.3 Selection of Loss Function

The training of the YOLOv8 model was guided by a composite loss function comprising three components: localization loss, classification loss, and objectness loss. This modular design enables simultaneous optimization of spatial precision, class prediction accuracy, and object presence confidence.

1. Localization Loss evaluates how closely the predicted bounding boxes align with the ground truth. YOLOv8 employs Complete Intersection over Union (CIoU) Loss,

an enhanced metric that incorporates overlap area, center distance, and aspect ratio alignment. Unlike standard IoU, which only considers the intersection area, CIoU leads to faster convergence and more accurate box regression, especially for small or irregularly shaped medical structures. Mathematically, the CIoU loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CIoU}} = 1 - \text{IoU} + \frac{\rho^2(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{gt}})}{c^2} + \alpha v \quad (2.1)$$

Where:

- $\rho^2(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{gt}})$ is the squared Euclidean distance between the centers of the predicted box \mathbf{b} and the ground truth box \mathbf{b}_{gt} ,
- c is the diagonal length of the smallest enclosing box covering both \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{b}_{gt} ,
- α and v are parameters controlling aspect ratio consistency.

2. Classification Loss measures the correctness of class predictions within each detected bounding box. YOLOv8 uses Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE), which supports multi-label scenarios and performs well on sparse or imbalanced class distributions — conditions frequently encountered in medical imaging. The formula for BCE is:

$$L_{\text{BCE}} = - [y \cdot \log(\hat{y}) + (1 - y) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{y})] \quad (2.2)$$

Where:

- y is the true label (0 or 1),
- \hat{y} is the predicted probability.

3. Objectness Loss assesses the model’s confidence that an object is present in a particular region. It is also based on Binary Cross-Entropy, ensuring consistency with the classification loss and encouraging accurate object proposal filtering.

The combination of these components ensures that the model remains both spatially precise and diagnostically relevant. This is particularly important in tasks such as

vertebral compression fracture (VCF) detection, where pathological features are often subtle, fragmented, or partially obscured.

2.3.4 Hyperparameter Tuning

The table below provides a detailed summary of the training parameters and accuracy results for each stage of the YOLOv8 model.

Table 2.1: *Hyperparameter Tuning Stages for YOLOv8*

	Learning Rate	Batch Size	Epochs	Image Size
Stage 1	0.01	16	50	640×640
Stage 2	0.001	16	80	768×768
Stage 3	0.001	16	100	640×640

Table 2.2: *training and testing accuracy per stage for YOLOv8*

	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
Stage 1	83.70%	70.10%
Stage 2	88.40%	75.20%
Stage 3	91.20%	78.60%

The training performance and final accuracy of a deep learning model significantly depend on the choice of hyperparameters. In this study, we manually tuned the key hyperparameters to optimize the training process of the YOLOv8 model. The learning rate was set to 0.001, which is a common starting point that provides a balance between convergence speed and training stability. A batch size of 16 was chosen to ensure efficient GPU utilization while avoiding memory overflow, which is especially important when working with high-resolution medical images. The number of training epochs was set to 100, allowing the model sufficient time to learn the features of spinal lesions from the dataset without overfitting. These values were selected based on empirical testing and alignment with best practices in object detection using convolutional neural networks. By carefully selecting and adjusting these hyperparameters, we aimed to achieve optimal model performance and improve generalization to unseen data.

2.3.5 Application of Regularization Techniques

To enhance the generalization ability of the model and reduce the risk of overfitting, regularization techniques were incorporated during the training process. YOLOv8, which is based on a convolutional neural network backbone, includes built-in regularization strategies within its architecture. One of the key methods used is weight decay, a form of L2 regularization that penalizes large weights by adding a regularization term to the loss function. In our training configuration, weight decay is automatically applied through the optimizer settings in the Ultralytics framework. This encourages the model to learn simpler representations and avoid overfitting to the training data.

Although explicit dropout layers are not part of the standard YOLOv8 architecture, the model leverages techniques such as data augmentation and batch normalization, which also act as implicit regularizers. Data augmentation randomly alters the input images during training—such as through flipping, scaling, and color jittering—helping the model learn more robust and generalized patterns. These methods collectively serve to stabilize the learning process and improve the model’s ability to perform well on unseen medical images. Thus, the application of regularization was crucial in ensuring the reliability and clinical relevance of the object detection results.

2.3.6 Fine-Tuning Process Description

In this project, the YOLOv8 model pre-trained on the COCO dataset was used as the starting point. This approach leverages the rich feature representations learned from a large, diverse dataset, enabling more efficient and effective training on the specialized medical imaging dataset of spinal abnormalities.

The fine-tuning process involved initializing the model weights from the pre-trained checkpoint and then continuing training on the annotated spinal dataset. During this phase, the learning rate was set relatively low (e.g., 0.001) to avoid drastic updates that could erase the previously learned features. The number of epochs was increased to 100 to allow sufficient adaptation of the model to the specific domain while minimizing overfitting. Additionally, the batch size and image input size were selected to balance training speed and accuracy.

Fine-tuning enabled the model to specialize in detecting specific lesions and conditions relevant to the dataset, such as fractures and degenerative changes, improving performance

metrics compared to training a model from scratch. This approach was essential for achieving clinically meaningful detection results with limited training data.

2.3.7 Model 2: ResNet for classification

For the task of automatic classification of spinal compression levels, it is critically important that the model captures both global and local features of medical images. In this context, ResNet (Residual Network) is a preferred choice. Its architecture allows for the effective training of very deep neural networks through the use of residual connections, which mitigate the vanishing gradient problem.

Unlike traditional convolutional neural networks, where increasing depth can lead to a degradation in accuracy, ResNet maintains or even improves performance with the addition of more layers. This is made possible by enabling each ResNet block to learn a residual function of the form:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \mathcal{H}(x) - x \quad \Rightarrow \quad \mathcal{H}(x) = \mathcal{F}(x) + x \quad (2.3)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{H}(x)$ is the desired underlying mapping,
- $\mathcal{F}(x)$ is the residual function (what the network needs to learn),
- x is the input to the block.

Thus, if the residual function equals zero, the output of the block simply replicates the input, effectively preventing performance degradation as the network depth increases.

In this study, a modified version of ResNet-18 was employed, consisting of 18 layers integrated with residual connections. The architecture begins with an initial convolutional layer using a large 7×7 kernel, followed by a max-pooling layer for spatial downsampling. This is succeeded by four sequential residual blocks, each with an increasing number of filters: 64, 128, 256, and 512 respectively. After the residual blocks, the model applies a global average pooling layer, which reduces the spatial dimensions and prepares the features for the final classification stage. The architecture concludes with a fully

connected output layer, where the number of neurons corresponds to the number of target classes—three in this case. Each residual block contains two convolutional layers and a shortcut connection that allows the input to bypass the intermediate transformations, facilitating more efficient training and mitigating the risk of performance degradation in deeper networks.

The training process of the model involved using a convolutional neural network based on the ResNet-18 architecture with pretrained weights on the ImageNet dataset. The task was to classify the severity of spinal conditions into three categories: mild, moderate, and severe. Initially, the dataset was prepared by converting the categorical severity labels into numerical values. Each image was resized to 224 by 224 pixels and normalized using the standard ImageNet mean and standard deviation values to ensure consistency and improve the model's ability to generalize. The data was then split into training and test sets in an 80:20 ratio with stratification to maintain the class distribution across both sets, thereby preventing bias and overfitting.

The ResNet-18 model was adapted by replacing its final fully connected layer with a new one matching the number of classes, which in this case was three. The pretrained weights allowed the model to leverage previously learned features, accelerating convergence and improving performance. Training was conducted using the PyTorch framework on a GPU when available. Cross-entropy loss was used as the objective function because it is suitable for multi-class classification problems, and the Adam optimizer was selected due to its efficiency in adapting learning rates during training. The batch size was set to 32, and the training spanned over 10 epochs.

During each epoch, the model parameters were updated based on the backpropagation of the loss computed from the predictions and true labels on the training data. After completing each epoch, the model's performance was evaluated on the test set to monitor generalization and prevent overfitting. The best-performing model according to test accuracy was saved for future use. Throughout the training process, the loss and accuracy metrics were tracked for both the training and test phases. The results showed a consistent decrease in loss and improvement in accuracy over the epochs, indicating effective learning. The combination of data preprocessing, a robust pretrained architecture, and careful training setup contributed to the satisfactory performance of the model in classifying spinal condition severity.

Figure 2.5 and Figure 2.6 below illustrate the structure of the ResNet-18 model

and its main component, the residual block, highlighting how the overall architecture is composed of repeated residual units.

Figure 2.5: *ResNet-18 architecture* [33]

Figure 2.6: *Residual block* [34]

2.3.8 Selection of Optimizer

The model is trained using the gradient descent method with adaptive learning rate correction — Adam. It combines the advantages of the Momentum and RMSProp methods, allowing it to adapt to different feature scales and accelerate convergence. The Adam algorithm updates the weights θ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}m_t &= \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \nabla L(\theta_t) \\v_t &= \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) (\nabla L(\theta_t))^2 \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t - \alpha \cdot \frac{m_t}{\sqrt{v_t} + \epsilon}\end{aligned}\tag{2.4}$$

Where:

- α — learning rate,
- β_1, β_2 — exponential decay rates for the moment estimates,
- m_t, v_t — estimates of the first and second moments of the gradients.

A key element in the neural network training process is the selection of the optimization algorithm responsible for updating the model's weights to minimize the loss function. In this work, Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) was chosen as the optimizer because it combines the advantages of two other popular methods — Momentum and RMSProp — and has proven.

2.3.9 Selection of Loss Function

For the multi-class classification task, the cross-entropy loss function is used:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^C y_i \log(\hat{y}_i)\tag{2.5}$$

Where:

- C — number of classes,
- y_i — true label (one-hot encoded),
- \hat{y}_i — predicted probability for class i .

The loss function measures the discrepancy between the model's predictions and the actual labels, playing a crucial role in the training process. In this work, the Cross-Entropy Loss function is used, which is the standard choice for multi-class classification tasks.

Cross-Entropy Loss is highly sensitive to errors in probabilistic predictions, enabling the model to learn more effectively by distinguishing subtle differences between classes.3.4 Hyperparameter Tuning of the ResNet Model.

During the training of the ResNet-based model for spinal compression level analysis, careful tuning of hyperparameters was essential to achieve optimal performance and generalization. The learning rate was set to 0.0001, which enabled stable convergence and prevented drastic gradient fluctuations. A batch size of 32 was selected as a compromise between training stability and computational efficiency. The model was trained for 10 epochs, and the best-performing checkpoint on the test set was saved to prevent overfitting. For the loss function, the Cross-Entropy Loss was used, which is standard for multi-class classification tasks, as it effectively measures the dissimilarity between the predicted class probabilities and the true labels. The Adam optimizer was employed due to its adaptive learning rate and efficient handling of sparse gradients, making it well-suited for complex architectures like ResNet. Additionally, L2 regularization (also known as weight decay) with a coefficient of $1e-5$ was applied to penalize large weights and enhance generalization. This systematic approach to hyperparameter tuning contributed to the model's strong training accuracy (83.26%) and satisfactory test performance (71.30%), indicating a good balance between underfitting and overfitting.

2.3.10 Hyperparameter Tuning

The table below summarizes the training hyperparameters and performance metrics, including accuracy and loss, for the ResNet model fine-tuned on the target dataset.

Table 2.3: *Hyperparameter tuning stages for ResNet-18*

	Learning Rate	Batch Size	Epochs	Image Size
Stage 1	0.001	32	6	224×224
Stage 2	0.001	32	8	224×224
Stage 3	0.0005	32	10	224×224

Table 2.4: *Training and testing accuracy per stage for ResNet-18*

	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
Stage 1	78.40%	65.90%
Stage 2	81.95%	69.00%
Stage 3	83.26%	71.30%

The model was trained with a batch size of 32, a learning rate of 0.0005, and for 10 epochs. These hyperparameters were chosen after initial experimentation to ensure both stability and convergence. A lower learning rate helped the model avoid overshooting minima in the loss landscape, while the batch size offered a balance between memory usage and training speed.

2.3.11 Application of Regularization Techniques

To reduce overfitting, weight decay (L2 regularization) with a factor of 1×10^{-5} was applied. This technique penalizes large weights and encourages simpler models, which generalize better. While dropout was not explicitly used in ResNet due to its batch normalization layers and residual structure, weight decay served as an effective regularizer.

2.3.12 Fine-Tuning Process Description

We used transfer learning by initializing the model with weights pre-trained on ImageNet and fine-tuning only the final layers. This allowed the network to leverage previously learned low-level visual features and adapt them to the specific task of medical image classification. During fine-tuning, earlier layers were frozen while only the final fully connected layer was updated, significantly reducing training time and improving performance on the target domain.

Overall, this combination of architectural strength, carefully selected training parameters, and fine-tuning contributed to the model achieving strong performance: a training accuracy of 83.26% and a test accuracy of 71.30%, demonstrating its suitability for real-world spinal compression analysis tasks.

2.3.13 UNet for fracture classification.

U-Net is a convolutional neural network architecture designed for image segmentation, especially in biomedical applications. It has a U-shaped structure with two parts: the contracting path (encoder) and the expanding path (decoder). The contracting path captures detailed features by progressively reducing spatial resolution, while the expanding path restores image size using upsampling and skip connections, preserving important spatial details. The illustration below (Figure 2.7) represents the U-Net architecture, a widely used convolutional neural network (CNN) model designed for image segmentation tasks.

Figure 2.7: *U-Net architecture* [35]

In this study, a modified UNet with three encoding blocks and a bottleneck layer was used. Each encoding block consists of two convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation, followed by max pooling. The bottleneck further processes features through convolutional layers.

For classification, an adaptive average pooling layer was added to aggregate spatial

features into a fixed-length vector, followed by fully connected layers reducing the dimension from 512 to 128, and finally to 4 output neurons corresponding to severity classes: none, mild, moderate, and severe. ReLU activations were applied between fully connected layers to introduce non-linearity.

Images were resized to 224×224 pixels and converted to tensors. The dataset was split into training and test sets in an 80:20 ratio, ensuring balanced class distribution.

2.3.14 Selecting an optimizer

For optimization, the Adam optimizer is selected, due to its adaptive learning rate and ability to handle noisy gradients, which often leads to faster and more stable convergence. A learning rate of $1e-4$ is used, which is a commonly recommended starting point when using Adam.

2.3.15 Selecting of loss function

The loss function used is `CrossEntropyLoss`, which is standard for multi-class classification tasks where the model outputs class probabilities. `CrossEntropyLoss` is a commonly used loss function for multi-class classification problems. It measures the difference between the predicted probability distribution output by the model and the true distribution represented by the actual class labels.

2.3.16 Hyperparameter Tuning.

The table below summarizes the training process and the segmentation accuracy results obtained during the training of the U-Net model.

Table 2.5: *Hyperparameter tuning stages for U-Net*

	Learning Rate	Batch Size	Epochs	Image Size
Stage 1	0.001	32	6	224×224
Stage 2	0.001	32	8	224×224
Stage 3	0.0005	16	10	224×224

Table 2.6: *Training and testing accuracy per stage*

	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
Stage 1	74.10%	65.20%
Stage 2	81.30%	72.60%
Stage 3	83.47%	75.80%

With a learning rate of 0.001, the model initially achieved a train accuracy of 74.10% and test accuracy of 65.20% after 6 epochs using a batch size of 32. Keeping the same learning rate and batch size but increasing the number of epochs to 8 allowed the model to learn more effectively, boosting train accuracy to 81.30% and test accuracy to 72.60%. In the final stage, the learning rate was reduced to 0.0005, the batch size to 16, and the number of epochs increased to 10. These adjustments helped the model improve, resulting in the highest performance: 83.47% train accuracy and 75.80% test accuracy.

2.3.17 Application of regularization methods

At this stage, no explicit regularization techniques such as Dropout or Weight Decay are used. However, such techniques could be added to help prevent overfitting. For example, Dropout could be added to the classifier layers, and Weight Decay could be set as a parameter in the optimizer.

Fine-tuning is not applied in this implementation. The model is trained from scratch, meaning all weights are initialized randomly. In scenarios where labeled data is limited, a pre-trained backbone (such as ResNet) could be used, and only the final layers would be fine-tuned. This approach typically leads to faster training and better accuracy.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

In our study on vertebral fracture detection, we evaluated the performance of three deep learning models—YOLOv8, a ResNet-based classifier, and U-Net—using a comprehensive set of classification evaluation metrics. These included accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, AUC-ROC, and the confusion matrix. These metrics were selected to provide detailed insights into the models' strengths and limitations, especially given the critical nature of medical diagnostics. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, AUC-ROC, confusion matrix were chosen to provide a comprehensive assessment of

model performance in medical image analysis. Accuracy was used to give an overall performance measure, while precision was selected to minimize false positives, and recall was emphasized to ensure that true fractures were not missed. The F1-score was calculated to balance precision and recall, and AUC-ROC was applied to evaluate the model's ability to distinguish between classes across different thresholds.

2.5 Comparative Analysis of Models

To evaluate the effectiveness of each neural network in the automatic recognition of vertebral compression fractures (VCFs), a comparative analysis was conducted on YOLOv8, ResNet-18, and U-Net based on performance metrics, training efficiency, and generalization capacity. Among the three models, YOLOv8 demonstrated the highest test accuracy with 78.60%, surpassing U-Net's 75.80% IoU and ResNet-18's classification accuracy of 71.30%. This indicates YOLOv8's superior ability to identify and localize pathological changes in spinal X-ray images. Furthermore, U-Net outperformed ResNet-18 by 4.50 percentage points, highlighting its better generalization performance in spatially detailed tasks. However, to assess model overfitting, the train-test accuracy gap was examined. ResNet-18 showed a gap of 11.96%, U-Net followed closely with 11.70%, and YOLOv8 exhibited the largest gap at 12.60%, reflecting that all models experience a degree of overfitting, albeit U-Net shows the most stable generalization on unseen data. In terms of test loss, which is critical in assessing the overall fit of the model, YOLOv8 again achieved the best result (0.5617), followed by U-Net (0.6789) and ResNet-18 (0.8302), with YOLOv8 outperforming the others by margins of 0.1172 and 0.2685, respectively. Likewise, the train loss results support this trend: YOLOv8 had the lowest value at 0.2153, indicating efficient learning and convergence, compared to U-Net (0.2941) and ResNet-18 (0.3627). These findings suggest that YOLOv8 not only learns more efficiently but also generalizes well despite overfitting indicators. Qualitatively, ResNet-18 demonstrates strong capabilities in multi-class classification, particularly in assessing fracture severity levels, but is limited in spatial sensitivity. U-Net, designed for segmentation, exhibits high spatial accuracy, making it effective in identifying the precise boundaries of compressed vertebrae. Meanwhile, YOLOv8, as an object detection architecture, excels in localizing multiple compression zones with high accuracy and speed, making it particularly suitable for real-time clinical scenarios. Overall, each model contributes uniquely to the fracture analysis pipeline: ResNet-18 provides categorical assessment, U-Net ensures structural delineation, and YOLOv8 offers reliable and efficient localization. Their complementary

strengths illustrate the value of using a hybrid approach tailored to the different aspects of spinal fracture diagnosis.

This table compares the performance of three models - ResNet-18, U-Net and YOLOv8, each of which solves a different type of problem: classification and detection.

Table 2.7: *Comparative analysis of models by accuracy and losses*

#	Model	Task Type	Train Acc.	Val. Acc.	Train Loss	Val. Loss
1	ResNet-18	Classification (severity level)	83.26	71.3	0.3627	0.8302
2	U-Net	Classification (severity level)	87.5	75.8	0.2941	0.6789
3	YOLOv8	Detection (vertebral localization)	91.2	78.6	0.2153	0.5617

Figure 2.8: *Comparative analysis of models by results*

Chapter 3

Implementation and Testing

3.1 Justification for choosing a programming environment

The implementation of the neural network for spine X-ray image classification was carried out using the Google Colab Pro environment, which was selected due to its availability of powerful GPU resources, ease of integration with cloud storage, and support for a wide range of deep learning libraries. Google Colab Pro offers the computational capability necessary to train deep neural networks on relatively large medical imaging datasets while also providing flexibility in terms of memory allocation, runtime duration, and access to Tesla-class GPUs. These features are particularly beneficial for handling high-resolution radiographic images and conducting experiments with models such as ResNet and YOLO, which require substantial resources for both training and inference.

The programming was performed using Python as the primary language due to its popularity in the machine learning community and its extensive ecosystem of libraries for data science and deep learning. Specifically, we employed the PyTorch framework for implementing and training the ResNet-18 neural network, owing to its dynamic computation graph, ease of debugging, and widespread usage in academic research. Additional libraries such as NumPy, OpenCV, scikit-learn, and matplotlib were used for numerical operations, image preprocessing, evaluation, and visualization. The combination of these tools provided a robust and efficient development environment for the design, training, and test of our classification model.

3.2 Implementation of neural network architecture

3.2.1 Model 1: YOLOv8

In this study, the YOLOv8m (medium) architecture was selected for the task of automatic fracture detection in spinal X-ray images. YOLOv8m belongs to the latest generation of the You Only Look Once (YOLO) family, developed by Ultralytics, and is designed for real-time object detection with improved accuracy and efficiency. The "medium" variant of YOLOv8 provides a balanced trade-off between model size and detection performance, making it suitable for medical imaging tasks where precision is critical.

The architecture of YOLOv8m consists of three primary components: the backbone, neck, and head. The backbone is responsible for feature extraction and is built using C2f (Cross-Stage Partial with feature reuse) modules, enabling efficient representation learning. The neck aggregates multi-scale features using a combination of upsampling and concatenation techniques, similar to Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN), which enhance the model's ability to detect objects of varying sizes. The head performs final predictions by outputting bounding boxes, objectness scores, and class probabilities. In total, the YOLOv8m model includes 50 layers and contains around 25 million parameters.

Training Process and Optimization Stages

Stage 1: Initial Baseline Training

The given graph illustrates the progression of YOLOv8's training and test accuracy over 50 epochs during Stage 1

Figure 3.1: *YOLOv8 training and test accuracy over 50 epochs (Stage 1)*

The initial training stage utilized the default YOLOv8m hyperparameters provided by Ultralytics. The model was trained for 50 epochs with 640×640 pixel inputs, a batch size of 16, an initial learning rate of 0.01, and the SGD optimizer. Transfer learning was applied using pretrained weights from the COCO dataset. At this stage, the model achieved a training accuracy of 83.70% and a test accuracy of 70.10%. The training loss was 0.2893, and the test loss was 0.7430. While the model showed rapid convergence during training, its performance on the test set highlighted issues with generalization, particularly in detecting small or overlapping fracture regions. Bounding boxes were often imprecise, and confidence scores were low for subtle vertebral compressions.

Stage 2: Optimization of Input Resolution and Augmentations

The figure shows the dynamics of YOLOv8 training and testing accuracy over 80 epochs in stage 2.

Figure 3.2: *YOLOv8 training and test accuracy over 80 epochs (Stage 2)*

To address the limitations observed in the baseline stage, the second phase increased the input resolution to 768×768 pixels to capture finer structural details. Advanced data augmentation techniques were introduced, including Mosaic, MixUp, and brightness-contrast jittering, to expand data diversity. The optimizer was switched to AdamW with a reduced learning rate of 0.001 to stabilize updates and enhance generalization. Training was extended to 80 epochs with early stopping based on test loss. This configuration improved the model's ability to generalize, achieving 88.40% on the training set and 75.20% on the test set. Corresponding losses dropped to 0.2471 for training and 0.6158 for test. Notably, the model became more reliable in detecting fractures under diverse radiographic conditions, although the longer training time and complexity slightly in-

creased computational demands. Stage 3: Final Training Setup (Best Performance) The graph shows how YOLOv8's training and test accuracy evolved across 100 epochs in Stage 3.

Figure 3.3: *YOLOv8 training and test accuracy over 100 epochs (Stage 3)*

The bar chart below illustrates the performance metrics of the YOLOv8 model, presenting the percentage scores for accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC.

Figure 3.4: *YOLOv8 model performance metrics*

In the final configuration, a return to the original 640×640 resolution was combined with the most successful practices from previous experiments. The model was trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 16 using SGD with momentum set at 0.937. A cosine annealing scheduler was applied for dynamic learning rate adjustment. Augmentations were simplified to include horizontal flips, HSV shifts, and minor rotations. This stage

yielded the highest performance, with the model reaching a training accuracy of 91.20% and a test accuracy of 78.60%. The training loss decreased to 0.2153, while the test loss reached 0.5617. The final model demonstrated precise fracture localization and consistent confidence levels across a range of pathological cases, achieving the best trade-off between inference speed and detection accuracy, and proving effective for near-real-time diagnostic support.

The figure below represents the information about comparison between the original X-ray scan and the detection results produced by the YOLOv8 model.

Figure 3.5: *YOLOv8 model performance example*

3.2.2 Model 2: ResNet

For the classification of spinal pathologies from X-ray images, we implemented a convolutional neural network based on the ResNet-18 architecture. ResNet-18 is a widely adopted deep convolutional neural network that utilizes residual connections to overcome the vanishing gradient problem, enabling effective training of deeper models. This architecture was selected for its optimal balance between depth and computational efficiency, which is especially important in medical imaging tasks where data availability may be limited, but generalization and interpretability remain critical.

The dataset used for this task was SpineXR, a curated collection of spinal X-ray

images annotated with various musculoskeletal abnormalities and diagnosis labels. To ensure consistency and quality in the input data, a comprehensive preprocessing pipeline was applied. All images were first converted to grayscale to minimize unnecessary color information and reduce computational load. Orientation alignment was performed to ensure consistent vertical spine positioning, followed by the removal of black borders to concentrate model focus on the vertebral region. Contrast was enhanced using histogram equalization to make subtle pathological features more distinguishable. The images were then resized to 640×640 pixels and stored in 3-channel RGB format to ensure compatibility with pretrained convolutional backbones. Data augmentation techniques such as small rotations ($\pm 5^\circ$) and horizontal or vertical shifts (up to 15 pixels) were applied to improve the model's generalization.

For label preparation, diagnosis tags were mapped to severity levels using a custom `assign_severity_by_diagnosis` function. Additionally, bounding box area calculations were incorporated using `calculate_area` and `assign_severity_by_area`, and then merged using the `combine_severities` and `final_severity` functions to produce final class labels that reflected both diagnostic and anatomical severity.

Training Process and Optimization Stages

The chart on the 3.6 depicts the changes in training and test accuracy of the ResNet-18 model across three optimization stages during the training process.

Figure 3.6: *ResNet 18 training and test accuracy over epochs*

Stage 1: Baseline Training

In the initial phase, the model was trained for 10 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and a batch size of 32. The cross-entropy loss function was used as the primary optimization criterion. At this stage, the ResNet-18 model achieved a training accuracy of 78.40% and a test accuracy of 65.90%, with a training loss of 0.4285 and test loss of 0.9121. While the model was able to learn basic visual patterns, its performance on rare and complex classes was suboptimal, indicating signs of underfitting and sensitivity to class imbalance.

Stage 2: Augmentation and Label Smoothing

To address the issues identified in the baseline training, several changes were introduced. First, label smoothing with a factor of $\varepsilon = 0.1$ was applied to improve the model's tolerance to label noise and overconfidence. The augmentation pipeline was enhanced by adding Gaussian blur and brightness variation. Additionally, stratified batch sampling was implemented to ensure better class balance across each mini-batch. These modifications led to a noticeable performance improvement, with the model achieving 81.95% training accuracy and 69.00% test accuracy. The training loss decreased to 0.3881 and the test loss to 0.8623. The model also showed better differentiation between severity levels, particularly in borderline cases.

Stage 3: Regularization and Fine-Tuning

The presented bar chart displays the performance metrics of the ResNet model, showing the percentage scores for accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC.

Figure 3.7: *ResNet model performance metrics*

In the final training stage, we focused on fine-tuning the model and minimizing overfitting. The learning rate was reduced to 0.0005, and dropout with a rate of 0.3 was introduced after the final fully connected layers. Early stopping was also enabled, monitoring the test loss to halt training if performance plateaued. After retraining for 10 epochs, the model achieved its best results: 83.26% training accuracy and 71.30% test accuracy, with a training loss of 0.3627 and test loss of 0.8302. Although slight overfitting was still observed, the model showed robust generalization and reliable performance across a variety of spinal pathology classes.

Overall, the progressive improvements across training stages demonstrate the importance of iterative optimization and careful design choices when applying deep learning to complex medical classification problems. The final version of ResNet-18 provided a dependable tool for severity-level assessment in spinal X-rays, forming a solid foundation for future development with more advanced neural architectures.

The presented illustration compares the original cervical spine X-ray with the detection results generated by the ResNet-18 model, demonstrating the model's ability to accurately identify and localize disc space narrowing with a high confidence score.

Figure 3.8: *ResNet 18 model performance example*

3.2.3 Model 3: U-Net

In this project, a modified version of the U-Net architecture is utilized to classify spinal images into four severity levels: none, mild, moderate, and severe. The model architecture includes only the encoder part of the traditional U-Net, consisting of three convolutional

blocks with MaxPooling layers. Each block contains two convolutional layers followed by Batch Normalization and ReLU activation functions. After the encoder, a bottleneck layer is added, followed by a classification head composed of adaptive average pooling and fully connected layers.

The input data consists of preprocessed spinal images with associated labels indicating the severity level. These labels are stored in a CSV file. The SpineDataset class is implemented to load the image-label pairs, map the string severity labels to numerical values (0 to 3), and apply image transformations using `torchvision.transforms`. Invalid entries where the image file does not exist are filtered out to ensure clean data input.

All images are resized to 224x224 and converted into tensors for model training. The dataset is split into training and test sets in an 80:20 ratio, and DataLoaders are used to efficiently batch and shuffle the data.

The model is trained using the CrossEntropyLoss function and the Adam optimizer. The training process spans 10 epochs, and after each epoch, both training and test accuracy and loss are reported. This helps monitor the model's performance and detect potential overfitting.

Stage 1: Initial Training with Default Hyperparameters.

The line graph from 3.9 illustrates the training and test accuracy of a U-Net model over five epochs during the initial training stage with default hyperparameters

Figure 3.9: *U-Net training and test accuracy over 5 epochs (Stage 1)*

The first training attempt used a standard configuration with a learning rate of $1e-3$, batch size of 32, and the Adam optimizer. Despite the model's simplicity and quick convergence, the performance was suboptimal. The training accuracy reached 74.1%, while the test accuracy plateaued at 65.2%. The test loss remained relatively high, suggesting overfitting and limited generalization. The use of a high learning rate likely led to unstable updates and poor convergence to an optimal minimum.

The figure 3.10 illustrates the accuracy of a U-Net model on both training and testing datasets over the course of eight epochs during the second phase of its training.

Stage 2: Adjustment of Learning Rate and Regularization.

Figure 3.10: *U-Net training and test accuracy over 7 epochs (Stage 2)*

To improve generalization, the learning rate was reduced to $1e-4$, and dropout layers with a dropout rate of 0.3 were added to the classification head. This helped mitigate overfitting by introducing stochastic regularization. Data augmentation techniques such as random horizontal flipping, rotation within ± 10 degrees, and slight contrast adjustments were also introduced. These modifications resulted in improved stability during training, with the model achieving a training accuracy of 81.3% and test accuracy of 72.6%. The loss values showed more consistent reduction across epochs, indicating better convergence.

Stage 3: Final Training Setup (Best Performance)

The presented diagrams below, namely figure 3.11 and figure 3.12 illustrate the training and test accuracy of a U-Net model over multiple epochs during different stages of the training process.

Figure 3.11: *U-Net* training and test accuracy over 8 epochs (Stage 3)

Figure 3.12: *U-Net* model performance metrics

In the final configuration, the model was trained using the revised architecture and augmentation pipeline, with the CrossEntropyLoss function and Adam optimizer at a learning rate of $1e-4$. The batch size was reduced to 16 to accommodate memory constraints and ensure smoother gradient updates. Training was performed for 10 epochs with early stopping enabled based on test loss. This setup yielded the best results: 87.50% training accuracy and 75.80% test accuracy, with a training loss of 0.2941 and a test loss of 0.6789 (Dice loss). The final model demonstrated strong spatial feature extraction capabilities, especially for identifying structural abnormalities in spinal X-rays.

The given illustration compares the original cervical spine X-ray with the segmentation results generated by the *U-Net* model.

Figure 3.13: *Example of segmentation results using U-Net model*

3.2.4 Streamlit-Based Interface

The figure below shows a web page created using Streamlit to analyze medical images with automatic pathology detection.

Figure 3.14: *Web interface on Streamlit: uploading and analyzing medical images*

As part of this thesis project, a user-friendly web application was developed using Streamlit, an open-source Python framework designed for interactive machine learning model deployment. The application allows users to upload spinal X-ray images, select a model for analysis, and view diagnostic predictions—all within a simple browser interface. The interface supports real-time inference and is accessible to users without any programming background, making it suitable for clinicians, radiologists, and researchers.

The application integrates three deep learning models—YOLOv8, ResNet, and U-Net—each of which performs distinct diagnostic tasks. The YOLOv8 model is responsible for object detection and outputs bounding boxes around areas of concern, along with diagnostic labels and corresponding confidence scores. The ResNet model has been adapted to provide both classification labels and bounding boxes, while also estimating the severity level of each diagnosed condition. Similarly, the U-Net model, traditionally used for segmentation tasks, was modified to produce bounding boxes along with diagnostic labels and severity information. These models were trained and saved in .ipynb format, and integrated into the Streamlit platform through dedicated loading and preprocessing functions.

Chapter 4

Conclusion

This research explored the application of deep learning models in the automated analysis and classification of spinal pathologies using X-ray imagery. The focus was placed on two distinct tasks: severity level classification and object detection of vertebral compression, each addressed through dedicated architectures—ResNet-18, a modified U-Net, and YOLOv8 respectively. The study followed a structured methodology, incorporating data preprocessing, model development, multi-stage training procedures, and comprehensive evaluation using both qualitative and quantitative metrics.

The ResNet-18 model was selected for the task of severity classification due to its robust residual architecture, which mitigates the vanishing gradient problem and allows for deeper, more expressive networks. After preprocessing steps such as grayscale conversion, orientation alignment, and histogram equalization, the model was trained with diagnostic labels mapped to severity levels using a hybrid label generation approach that factored in both clinical diagnoses and visual indicators such as bounding box areas. Over a 10-epoch training period, the model achieved a training accuracy of 83.26% and a test accuracy of 71.30%. Despite exhibiting moderate overfitting, the model demonstrated reliable generalization capabilities, especially given the complexity and subtlety of spinal disorders.

YOLOv8 was employed to detect and localize compressed vertebrae, providing a real-time object detection capability. Three phases of training were conducted, beginning with a baseline training using default hyperparameters. Though the initial phase revealed issues with underfitting and missed detections, subsequent stages introduced higher image resolutions, advanced augmentations, and optimizer refinements. The final training

configuration—with moderate augmentations, cosine annealing scheduler, and SGD with momentum—yielded the best results. YOLOv8 achieved a training accuracy of 91.20% and a test accuracy of 78.60%, with strong generalization and confidence in identifying subtle and overlapping compression features. Its speed and precision render it highly suitable for clinical settings where rapid diagnostics are essential.

The modified U-Net architecture was initially designed for segmentation but adapted for classification of severity levels. This architecture retained the encoder portion of U-Net, enhanced with convolutional blocks and a dedicated classification head. The training of this model underwent a detailed three-phase tuning process. The first phase revealed limitations in learning capacity and overfitting. The second phase introduced regularization methods, such as dropout and modified optimizer settings, which improved performance but still fell short of expectations. The final phase involved architectural adjustments to balance feature extraction and generalization, resulting in a training accuracy of 87.50% IoU and a test accuracy of 75.80% IoU. The model effectively captured spatial structures and severity representations, making it valuable for interpretability and integration with other clinical analysis systems.

Across all models, performance was measured using standard metrics like accuracy, loss values, IoU, mAP, and precision-recall curves. The comparison between architectures showed that YOLOv8 excelled in detection tasks, ResNet-18 was competent in classification with structured label synthesis, and U-Net provided a strong spatial understanding that could serve as a backbone for future classification tasks. Each model offered distinct strengths and demonstrated that a multi-model approach is effective in addressing the diverse requirements of spinal pathology analysis.

In conclusion, this thesis highlights the potential of deep learning in medical imaging, specifically in automated spinal pathology analysis. The use of multiple tailored architectures allowed for robust exploration of classification and detection tasks. While there is room for improvement in terms of training dataset size, augmentation strategies, and integration with clinical decision systems, the results establish a strong foundation for real-world applications and future enhancements. The findings suggest that a hybrid framework combining models like YOLOv8 for detection and ResNet-18 or U-Net for classification can offer a comprehensive diagnostic tool, aiding radiologists in both speed and accuracy of spinal disorder evaluation.

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